

Evaluation of the Mean Activity Coefficient of the Ions of Strong Electrolytes in Solutions whose Concentration varied from 0.001 M to 4 M

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Manuscript received 25 August 1981, revised 7 January 1982, accepted 28 April 1982

In previous publications, the author has deduced an equation to account for the variation of the mean activity coefficient of the ions of strong electrolytes of 1:1 type in solutions of low concentrations, 0.001 to 0.1 m, by modifying the Debye-Hückel expression for k . This equation has been combined with that derived by Glueckauf to account for the effect of hydration on the activity coefficient of ions of the aforesaid type, using volume fraction statistics. The combined equation has been subjected to test using the data available in the literature on HCl, LiCl, NaCl, KCl and CsCl in the concentration range 0.2 m to 4 m and has been found satisfactory.

It follows from the treatment developed by Robinson and Stokes¹ and by Glueckauf^{2,3} that in the case of aqueous solutions of strong electrolytes, the effects of (i) interionic attraction and (ii) of hydration on the mean molal activity coefficient, γ , of the ions in the region above 0.1 M may be represented by the following expression:

$$\log \gamma = \log \gamma^{el} + \log \gamma^s \quad \dots (1)$$

Robinson and Stokes¹ have identified $\log \gamma^{el}$ with the Debye-Hückel expression, $\frac{A(Z^+)(Z^-)\sqrt{I}}{1+B_a\sqrt{I}}$, and for $\log \gamma^s$ they have derived an expression using mole fraction statistics.

Denoting $\log \gamma^s$ by $\log \gamma^{vts}$, and using volume fraction statistics, Glueckauf^{2,3} derived an expression which, after neglecting some minor terms, may be written as

$$\log \gamma^s = \log \gamma^{vts} = \frac{0.018 \text{ mr} (r+h-v)}{2.3 v (1+0.018 \text{ mr})} + \frac{h-v}{v}$$

$$\log (1+0.018 \text{ mr}) - \frac{h}{v} \log (1-0.18 \text{ mh}) \quad \dots (3)$$

where r = (apparent molar volume of electrolyte at $m=1$ for 1:1 electrolyte)/(molar volume of water), h = hydration number and v = the number of ions formed by a molecule. For $\log \gamma^{el}$, Glueckauf³ also used the Debye-Hückel expression besides a function $X_{(m)}$, which becomes significant above 0.1 m. According to him upto $m=3$, the $X_{(m)}$ function follows the empirical equation $X_{(m)} =$

$$-0.06 \left[\frac{m}{1+0.5 m} \right]^3$$

He also found³, as suggested by Bjerrum, that when the concentration of the electrolyte was appreciably above 0.1 m, $\log \gamma^{el}$ could be replaced empirically by $-K m^{\frac{1}{2}}$ where K is a constant.

The values of γ calculated by using the equations of Robinson and Stokes and of Glueckauf have been found to agree well with the experimental data, but Glueckauf's equation based on volume fraction statistics has got some other advantages which have been acknowledged by Robinson and Stokes also. Therefore, the equation obtained by combining the expression for $\log \gamma^{el}$ deduced by the author with that for $\log \gamma^{vts}$ deduced by Glueckauf has been used in this paper.

Deduction of the combined equation: In previous publications^{4,5}, by modifying the expression for k of the Debye-Hückel theory, the author has derived equations which can account for the variation of mean molar activity coefficient of the ions of strong electrolytes at low concentrations viz., 0.001 m to 0.1 m.

The equation for 1:1 electrolytes may be written as

$$\log y = -[(B)/(A)^{\frac{1}{2}}][C^{\frac{1}{2}} - C_0^{\frac{1}{2}}] \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

$$= -[(B)/(A)^{\frac{1}{2}}](C)^{\frac{1}{2}} + a_0 \quad \dots \quad (4a)$$

In equation (4), B is a constant whose value can be calculated from theory, A represents the effective ionic diameter and C_0 , which is a very small constant, may be interpreted to represent the concentration at which y becomes unity. In equation (4a), $a_0 = [(B)/(A)^{\frac{1}{2}}](C_0)^{\frac{1}{2}}$ and hence it is a small constant.

When the concentration of the electrolyte is low, $\log \gamma^{el}$ is to be identified with $\log y$ of equation (4) or (4a). For high concentrations, adopting the usual relation, $\gamma = \left[\frac{c}{m d_0} \right] y$ it follows from equation

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TABLE 1—VARIATION OF MEAN ACTIVITY COEFFICIENT OF IONS WITH DILUTION AT 25°

Miscellaneous	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
HCl	m=c	0.001	0.002	0.005	0.01	0.02	0.05	0.1
Eqn. (4a)								
B/(A) ^{1/2} = 0.237	Obs. γ	0.965	0.953	0.929	0.905	0.876	0.830	0.794
(A) = (2.63) ² Å								
a ₀ = 0.0086	Cal. γ	0.966	0.952	0.929	0.907	0.880	0.834	0.792
HCl	m	0.2	0.3	0.5	0.7	1.0	2.0	
Eqn. (6)	C	0.1987	0.2975	0.4940	0.6890	0.9788	1.921	
B/(A) ^{1/2} = 0.237	Obs. γ	0.767	0.756	0.757	0.772	0.809	1.009	
r = 1.05								
h = 5.34	Cal. γ	0.774	0.763	0.762	0.772	0.804	0.997	
LiCl	m	0.2	0.3	0.5	0.7	1.0	2.0	
Eqn. (6)	C	0.1987	0.2975	0.4940	0.6890	0.9788	1.921	
B/(A) ^{1/2} = 0.263	Obs. γ	0.757	0.744	0.739	0.748	0.774	0.921	
(A) = (2.37) ² Å								
r = 1.03	Cal. γ	0.752	0.741	0.736	0.748	0.781	0.998	
h = 5.60								
NaCl	m=c	0.001	0.002	0.005	0.01	0.02	0.05	0.1
Eqn. (4a)								
B/(A) ^{1/2} = 0.265	Obs. γ	0.965	0.952	0.927	0.902	0.871	0.819	0.774
(A) = [(2.35) ²] Å								
a ₀ = 0.0113	Cal. γ	0.966	0.950	0.925	0.900	0.870	0.820	0.778
NaCl	m	0.2	0.3	0.5	1.0	2.0		
Eqn. (6)	C	0.1987	0.2975	0.4940	0.9788	1.921		
B/(A) ^{1/2} = 0.265	Obs. γ	0.734	0.710	0.682	0.658	0.671		
r = 1.03	Cal. γ	0.727	0.708	0.676	0.654	0.682		0.1
h = 4.06								
KCl	m=c	0.001	0.002	0.005	0.01	0.02	0.05	0.1
Eqn. (4a)								
B/(A) ^{1/2} = 0.265	Obs. γ	0.965	0.952	0.927	0.902	0.869	0.816	0.768
(A) = [(2.35) ²] Å								
a ₀ = 0.011	Cal. γ	0.965	0.950	0.924	0.899	0.869	0.819	0.778
KCl	m	0.2	0.3	0.5	1.0	2.0	3.0	4.0
Eqn. (6)	C	0.1983	0.2965	0.4914	0.9689	1.883	2.744	3.553
B/(A) ^{1/2} = 0.265	Obs. γ	0.717	0.687	0.650	0.605	0.575	0.573	0.582
r = 1.4	Cal. γ	0.714	0.685	0.648	0.602	0.578	0.575	0.592
h = 3.0								
CsCl	m	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4			
Eqn. (4a)	C	0.0993	0.1978	0.2955	0.3925			
B/(A) ^{1/2} = 0.30	Obs. γ	0.759	0.700	0.664	0.638			
(A) = [(2.08) ²] Å								
a ₀ = 0.02	Cal. γ	0.761	0.700	0.661	0.632			
CsCl	m	0.5	1.0	3.0	4.0			
Eqn. (6)	C	0.4886	0.9578	1.840	2.653	3.399		
B/(A) ^{1/2} = 0.30	Obs. γ	0.606	0.544	0.496	0.479	0.474		
r = 2.3	Cal. γ	0.608	0.545	0.495	0.478	0.474		
h = 2.4								

(4a), neglecting a₀, that :

$$\log \gamma^{el} = \log \left(\frac{c}{md_0} \right) \gamma = - \left[\frac{B}{(A)^{1/2}} \right] (C)^{1/2} + \log \left[\frac{c}{md_0} \right] \quad (5)$$

where d₀ represents the density of the solvent.

Now substituting in equation (1) the values of log γ^{el} and log γ^{vis} as recorded in the equations (5) and (3) it may be written as

$$\log \gamma = - \left[\frac{B}{(A)^{1/2}} \right] (C)^{1/2} + \log \left(\frac{c}{md_0} \right) + \frac{0.018 \text{ m} r (r+h-v)}{2.3 v (1+0.018 \text{ m} r)} + \frac{h-v}{v} \log (1+0.018 \text{ m} r) - \frac{h}{v} \log (1-0.018 \text{ m} h) \quad (6)$$

At 25°, B and d₀ in equation (6) are 0.624 and 0.997 respectively in aqueous solution.

In the following section of the paper, the validity of each of the equations (4a) and (6) has been subjected to test using preferably such electrolytes, the data on the mean activity coefficient of which at 25°, are available both in the low concentration range 0.001 to 0.1 m and the high concentration range 0.2 to 4 m.

Processing of data: The data on the mean activity coefficient of the ions of some 1 : 1 electrolytes in aqueous solution at 25° are recorded in Table 1. In column 1 of the table, under the head miscellaneous, are mentioned the electrolyte and the equation used and the values of the constants in the equation. For dilute solutions upto 0.1 N we have taken molar concentration C = m, molal concentration. For the concentrated solutions, C has

been calculated using the equation $C/m = d_0 - Am + Bm^2$ (vide Harned and Owen⁶). Cal. γ and Obs. γ represent the calculated and observed values of the mean activity coefficients. For C corresponding to $m=1$ an approximate value of 'h' is first found which yields γ of the right magnitude. The value of h is then adjusted by trial so as to yield values of γ in close agreement with the observed ones over as wide a range of C as possible.

For the dilute solutions of the electrolytes, the data on HCl, NaCl and KCl have been collected from Shedlovsky's paper⁷. The data on concentrated solutions of HCl, LiCl and CsCl have been collected from Robinson and Stokes book¹ (pp. 491-495, Tables 9-11), and those on NaCl and KCl have been collected from Harned and Owen's book⁶ [p. 731, Table (12-3-1A)].

Discussion

It will be noticed from the data recorded in Table 1 that in the concentration range 0.001 to 0.1 m the calculated values of γ agree well with those observed for the electrolytes HCl, NaCl and KCl, the data of which are available at 25° in the aforesaid concentration range. In the case of CsCl a few data are available at 25° in the concentration range below 0.1 m but the equation (4a) holds good upto 0.4 m, and above that equation (6) holds good.

At high concentrations recorded in Table 1, the agreement between the calculated and observed values of γ may be considered satisfactory upto 1.0 m for HCl, LiCl and NaCl, upto 3.0 m for KCl and upto 4.0 m for CsCl.

It may be pointed out that the value of $(B)/(A)^{\frac{1}{2}}$ calculated by using equation (4a) in the low concentration range, where data are available, remains unchanged when equation (6) is used for calculating γ of the same electrolyte in the high concentration range.

It may be mentioned that the value of 'h' of an electrolyte calculated by using equation (6) differs somewhat from that calculated by Glueckauf^{2,3}. The difference, however, is not much; for example in the case of KCl, where the percentage difference is maximum, $h=3.0$ according to equation (6) and 2.58 according to Glueckauf^{2,3}.

This difference in the values of 'h' does not affect the approximately linear relationship between 'h' and $\frac{1}{r}$ (where r is the Pauling radius) observed by Glueckauf². It only alters the slope of the straight line.

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